

Gamified Latin Learning – Using Game Based Immersive Learning and Natural Language Processing to Teach Latin

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Abstract. Video games have been steadily increasing in popularity since the early 1950s, with the creation of new platforms and more complex systems. By using immersive learning, where users can practice skills in virtual environments, this study explores the use of video games as a teaching tool for languages where no native speakers remain such as Latin. The motivation for this work stems from the need for more effective, engaging methods to learn ancient languages that lack natural conversational contexts. Traditional memorization-based methods are often limited in sustaining learner motivation, while immersive approaches can replicate real, communicative environments. Natural Language Processing (NLP) models such as BERT can be used to automate the process of grammar correction to improve a user’s vocabulary and grammar when interacting with non-player characters. We fine-tuned BERT on synthetically generated Latin error-correction data and integrated it into the game environment to provide real-time grammatical feedback to learners. Our results showed that model achieved high accuracy in detecting verb and noun errors, though its performance on adjective errors was less robust. Overall, the findings highlight the feasibility and promise of combining feedback from state-of-the-art large-language models (LLM) with game-based immersive learning to enhance Latin acquisition.

Keywords: Natural Language Processing, Gamification, Grammar Error Correction, BERT, Synthetic Data Generation.

1 Introduction

Video games have grown in popularity since their early inception in the 1950s. One of the first examples was a tic-tac-toe inspired game called 'OXO', created by British Professor, Alexander Douglas, on an Electronic Delay Storage Automatic Calculator (EDSAC) computer [1]. Since then, video games have evolved with consoles and advanced graphics. As of December 2023, 77% of adults aged 18-29 play video games weekly, with an estimated number of 3.38 billion players worldwide [2]. Video games can provide benefits such as promoting creativity, improving cognitive and social skills,

and developing problem-solving abilities [3]. Given their popularity and potential, it is important to explore video games as a teaching tool.

Immersive learning enables subjects to acquire skills through practice in simulated environments, often using Virtual or Augmented Reality. This approach allows repetitive skill development and is commonly used in healthcare training for high-risk procedures [4]. According to Krashen [5] true language proficiency can only be achieved through Acquisition learning. Immersive learning can simulate language environments, which is especially useful for ancient languages with no native speakers, such as Latin.

Latin originated in central Italy, with records dating to the seventh century BCE [6]. Today, the main forms of Latin are Archaic Latin (1200–700 BCE), Classical Latin (100 BCE–450 CE), and Ecclesiastical Latin. Although rarely used, Latin influences modern languages such as English, Spanish, and French, and remains in religious, legal, and medical terminology. Learning Latin is challenging due to the absence of native speakers, and effective resources are scarce.

Over the past four decades, language learning tools have evolved from textbook-based and classroom instruction to computer-assisted language learning, and more recently to mobile and Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based systems such as Duolingo, Babbel, and Rosetta Stone. These tools focus primarily on living languages and vocabulary memorization, leaving historical and low-resource languages like Latin underserved. By combining immersive gameplay with automated Natural Language Processing (NLP) feedback, this study addresses that gap.

Learning languages requires making and correcting mistakes. AI, particularly NLP, can help by analysing text and understanding human language [7]. This study develops an immersive Latin-learning game in Unity, integrating a BERT-based grammatical error-correction model trained on synthetic data. The system gives real-time feedback to support learning, and its effectiveness is evaluated against a traditional vocabulary-study control group.

This study aimed at answering the following research questions:

- Does immersive learning improve the retention of Latin vocabulary more effectively than traditional learning approaches?
- Is an NLP-based grammatical error correction model effective for Latin learners?

2 Related Work

Research in second language acquisition (SLA) spans traditional theories and modern computational approaches. Krashen's Input Theory (1980s) distinguishes between acquisition, a subconscious process like children learning through exposure, and learning, a conscious effort involving memorisation [5]. Though criticised for ambiguity, Luo notes that traditional classrooms emphasise learning, while communicative activities better support acquisition.

This gap has driven interest in immersive learning, which shows strong empirical support. A 2023 study found that participants in immersive settings achieved higher

TOEFL scores after six months, suggesting acquisition-based environments enhance fluency [8].

Researchers have also examined video games as learning tools, providing interactive spaces that boost engagement and motivation [9]. While several game design patterns encourage learning through rewards, few provide objective frameworks for developers.

Alongside these approaches, modern pedagogical methods such as task-based and blended learning further promote meaningful, activity-based learning across online and in-person contexts [10]. Collaborative and autonomous learning empower students to take responsibility for progress, while authentic materials expose them to real-world language use. Together, these methods complement one another to support successful language learning.

Complementing these pedagogical developments, computational tools have increasingly been applied to SLA. The Classical Language Toolkit (CLTK), for example, applies NLP to historical languages such as Latin and Ancient Greek [11], offering tokenization, tagging, and lemmatization functions.

Recent advances in Transformer-based models have further reshaped the field of NLP. Transformers use self-attention to capture relationships between words regardless of position, surpassing the performance of previous RNN and CNN models [12]. Features like multi-head attention and positional encoding features of Transformer enable state-of-the-art performance in translation and other NLP tasks. Pre-trained language models such as BERT leverage bidirectional context and unsupervised training for improved accuracy [13] [14].

These advances have enabled applications like Grammatical Error Correction (GEC), where transformer-based models detect and correct text errors. GECToR, for instance, uses sequence tagging for faster, precise inference [15]. It assigns tags such as \$KEEP and \$APPEND to learn grammar patterns while avoiding overcorrection.

Because annotated GEC corpora are scarce, especially for historical languages, researchers use tag-based synthetic data generation to create realistic error-correction pairs [16]. Models trained on such data achieve results comparable to those using manually annotated corpora.

In summary, while prior research has explored immersive learning and NLP for modern languages, little work addresses historical or extinct ones such as Latin. Gaps remain in integrating grammatical feedback models into interactive learning environments and assessing learner outcomes. This study aims to fill these gaps by developing an immersive Latin-learning game with integrated NLP-based correction and comparing it to traditional vocabulary learning.

3 Methodology

Using the Unity game development application, we created a video game which interfaces with a Flask-based NLP server to deliver real-time grammatical feedback, integrating the BERT model, correction pipeline, and game UI into a unified learning workflow (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Overview of the overall system architecture

3.1 Game Creation

The prototype was developed in Unity, a widely used cross-platform game engine for creating interactive 2D and 3D applications [17], as an exploratory learning environment where players navigate a fictional medieval-style village while engaging entirely in Latin (Fig. 2). This provides an immersive backdrop without replicating specific historical locations.

Fig. 2: Player interaction with NPCs and vocabulary in a game mission

Core mechanics support contextual vocabulary acquisition with interactions with non-player characters (NPCs). Objects in the environment carry Latin labels, reinforcing word associations through repeated exposure. NPC dialogue integrates context clues and multiple-choice responses, aiding learning in gradual language comprehension. This design values learning through interaction rather than formal instruction. Players are encouraged to retry answering questions until they arrive at the correct response.

3.2 Scriptwriting and Latin Translation

Dialogue was first drafted in English to control flow and align with pedagogical principles [10]. Phrases supported step-by-step understanding within task-based missions,

following Task-Based Learning and Krashen’s Acquisition-Learning Hypothesis [5]. The text was then translated into Latin using online resources [18] [19], and Lingua Latina per se illustrata [20] with ChatGPT used to verify accuracy before testing.

3.3 Spelling Correction

To ensure vocabulary accuracy, player input was matched to the nearest valid word using the RapidFuzz Python library [21]. RapidFuzz operates on a modified Latin Dictionary Database [22], augmented with tokens derived from the training dataset, allowing for faster string-similarity scoring (with exact matches receiving a score of 100). The entire procedure runs in the background (Fig. 3) without revealing scores to the player.

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Fetching lexicon...
Processing: Puellq cantat
Correcting spelling...
Correcting 'Puellq' to 'puella' (same length, score: 83.33333333333334)
Correcting 'cantat' to 'cantat' (same length, score: 100.0)

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Fig. 3: Sample output after inputting sentence with wrong spelling

3.4 Synthetic Data Generation

Due to limited Latin-focused training data, a custom dataset was created from a Latin wordlist obtained from the Open Text Archive [22] and parsed using CLTK [11]. POS tagging, Collatinus Decliner–based morphological analysis, and word embeddings[23] [24] were used to structure words into nouns, verbs, and adjectives in a CSV file (Table 1).

Table 1: Sample from CSV file of Latin vocabulary divided into nouns, verbs, and adjectives.

Noun	Verb	Adjective
porcus	circumiro	cliuosus
interiungus	reseruo	moluus
manvs	amatho	semiplens
humo	seuoco	torridus

Correct sentences were generated using a generic adjective-subject-object-verb structure, ensuring agreement in case, number, and gender [25], and then passed to a custom error injector inspired by GECToR [15] and synthetic data generation [16] methods. Each word received a tag (\$KEEP for unchanged words, other errors seen in Fig. 4) and combined with correct and incorrect sentences to form training rows (Fig. 5).

3.6 Model Loading in Unity

The trained BERT model was integrated into Unity to analyse player input and provide corrections. Since Unity uses C#, Python scripts were interfaced via a Flask web server [28]. The first script loaded the model and tokenizer, tokenized input from unity, predicted error tags, and used CLTK with the Collatinus Decliner to generate corrected tokens. The second script launched the Python process in a dedicated environment to manage dependencies. Finally, the model was connected to in-game UI elements, allowing player input to be sent via HTTP POST to the Flask API and receive real-time corrections.

3.7 Synthetic Data and Model Evaluation

To assess the quality of the generated Latin sentences, manual verification was performed on an initial sample of 20 rows, comparing each word in the correct and error-injected sentences against online resources [18] [19]. Although sentences were grammatically correct, they lacked logical meaning. Random samples were further checked during training. The BERT model was evaluated using standard metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and f1-score [29] [30]. Accuracy measures how many total predictions the model gets right. Precision reflects how often the model's corrections are correct, while recall reflects how many actual errors the model successfully detects. The f1-score balances precision and recall, and the additional f0.5 metric emphasized precision, prioritizing correct error-identification over false predictions [31]. These metrics are standard in NLP because they evaluate both correctness and error-detection quality in token classification.

3.8 Learning Evaluation

Learning evaluation involved sixteen testers between 25–35 years old, all native English speakers with zero-to-amateur Latin proficiency, recruited through convenience sampling and personal networks. All participants were monolingual with similar backgrounds of learning Irish and either French or German in primary and secondary school, with little-to-no retained knowledge of the mentioned languages. Participants were split into Group A, who played the game, and Group B, who used a custom Latin vocabulary sheet. Group A attended small sessions and played the game for one hour. Group B studied vocabulary from the given sheet for one hour. Both groups completed three forms: Form A, which was given prior to learning and assessed their starting knowledge, Form B, which was given immediately after learning, and Form C, which was given a day after and assessed their retained knowledge. Form C combined all questions from Forms A and B to evaluate both immediate and retained learning. Question order within each form was shuffled to minimise order effects and familiarity bias.

While test content overlapped to measure retention, this approach helped reduce test–retest bias by preventing participants from simply memorising question order.

The vocabulary sheet mirrored the words used in the in-game dialogue and included Latin terms, English translations, and grammatical information. All questionnaire translations were verified using previously mentioned online resources and ChatGPT to ensure accuracy. Forms assessed Sentence Translation, Fill in the Blanks, and Reading Comprehension, with question order randomised to prevent order effects.

Python scripts using pandas [32] processed the responses, calculated participant and group scores, identified best/worst answered questions, and generated graphs comparing average individual and group performance. Manual corrections were applied where a participant accidentally chose the wrong group.

3.9 Ethical Considerations

All participation was voluntary, and participants could withdraw at any time. The Unity game collected no personal identifiers, and no game data was saved. Participants were over eighteen and provided consent. Names entered in the forms were optional (nicknames allowed) and used only to track responses. All collected names were excluded from figures and are stored securely in raw CSV files. No other personal information was collected, and all questions answered voluntarily.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Model Evaluation

The BERT token classification model demonstrated strong performance overall, achieving a total accuracy of 94.44%, though averaging per-tag accuracies reduced this to 86.13%, highlighting some imbalance in the dataset. Verb-based tags showed the strongest results, with person error tags achieving 100% accuracy and number tags above 97%, indicating the model effectively learns verb conjugation patterns. Noun-based tags also performed well, with case errors averaging 96% accuracy. However, certain number-based noun errors, such as plural-to-singular, were slightly weaker, showing potential ambiguity in the tagging process. Adjective-based tags were the weakest, with the masculine-to-feminine error tags reaching only 61% accuracy, due to overlapping word endings across genders (-is, -es, -ies), as shown in Table 2. Incorporating declension information could improve performance for these cases.

Table 2: Combined samples taken from three files showing all adjectives, separated by gender.

Masculine	Feminine	Neuter
abietarius	abietaria	abominabile
abominabiles	abietariae	abominabilia

abominabilis	abominabilis	abominabilie
absimiles	abominabilis	absimilia
absoluti	absimiles	absolutum
absurdi	absoluta	absurda
absurdus	absolutae	accensibilia
accensibilis	absurda	accensibilie
acceptabiles	absurdae	acceptabile

The \$KEEP tag, representing words requiring no change, achieved 97.43% accuracy, indicating that the model rarely produces false corrections. Per-class precision, recall and F1-scores (Fig. 6) showed consistent high scores for verb-based tags, and sub 80% for the majority of adjective-based tag scores. Sample predictions showed the model correctly identified errors in both dataset and unseen sentences but occasionally misclassified fully correct sentences.

Classification Report:				
	precision	recall	f1-score	support
ADJ_CASE_a-n	0.7921	0.8000	0.7960	100
ADJ_GENDER_f-m	0.8857	0.9300	0.9073	100
ADJ_GENDER_f-n	0.6033	0.7300	0.6606	100
ADJ_GENDER_m-f	0.6630	0.6100	0.6354	100
ADJ_GENDER_m-n	0.6098	0.7500	0.6726	100
ADJ_GENDER_n-f	0.7453	0.7900	0.7670	100
ADJ_GENDER_n-m	0.7300	0.7300	0.7300	100
ADJ_NUMBER_p-s	0.9213	0.8200	0.8677	100
ADJ_NUMBER_s-p	0.5913	0.6800	0.6326	100
KEEP	0.9968	0.9743	0.9854	5100
NOUN_CASE_a-n	0.7442	0.9600	0.8384	100
NOUN_CASE_n-a	0.8348	0.9600	0.8930	100
NOUN_NUMBER_p-s	0.8500	0.8500	0.8500	100
NOUN_NUMBER_s-p	0.8571	0.9600	0.9057	100
VERB_NUMBER_p-s	0.9604	0.9700	0.9652	100
VERB_NUMBER_s-p	0.9340	0.9900	0.9612	100
VERB_PERSON_1-3	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	100
VERB_PERSON_2-3	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	100
accuracy			0.9444	6800
macro avg	0.8177	0.8614	0.8371	6800
weighted avg	0.9494	0.9444	0.9462	6800

Fig 6.: Evaluation metrics calculated for the final model.

4.2 Experimental Data Results

Sixteen participants were split into Group A (game-based learning) and Group B (vocabulary sheet). Baseline scores (Form A) were similar: Group A 40.38%, Group B 34.13%. Immediate learning (Form B) showed Group A improved by 49.54% to 89.92% average accuracy, while Group B improved by 22.72% to 56.85%. Retention (Form C) showed a slight decline for Group A to 87.94%, and an improvement for Group B to 66.89% (Fig. 7). Individual analysis revealed consistent gains among game-based learners (most 40–70%), while classroom learners showed varied outcomes, including minimal gains and two zero scores. Overall, Group A demonstrated more

uniform and substantial progress, whereas Group B's improvement was less consistent (Fig. 8). The x-axis represents the three assessment forms (A, B, C), and the y-axis shows mean scores as percentages.

Fig. 7: Per group performance on all forms showing baseline, immediate, and retention.

Fig. 8: Individual performance of all participants based on group.

5 Conclusion

This study integrated a large pre-trained language model (BERT) into a Unity-based game to support learning Latin language. More specifically, a BERT-based token classification model trained on synthetically generated Latin data enabled real-time grammatical error correction. The model performed well on verb and noun tags but struggled with adjectives due to overlapping gender forms.

The study involved two groups: Group A, who engaged in game-based learning, and Group B, who received traditional classroom instruction. Results showed that game-based learners consistently outperformed classroom learners, supporting the hypothesis that immersive learning enhances short-term vocabulary acquisition. Since testing spanned only two days, conclusions about long-term retention remain tentative, serving as proof-of-concept evidence of short-term learning benefits.

The study confirmed that immersive learning produced higher immediate gains, and the NLP-based model was effective overall, particularly for verbs and nouns. Limitations include a small sample size ($n=16$), limited demographic data, and no significance testing, restricting generalisability.

Overall, the study demonstrates that combining gamified learning with LLM-based feedback can effectively support ancient language education, showcasing the potential of AI-driven learning tools. Future work should improve adjective detection, expand datasets with fully correct examples, and test with larger, more diverse groups, while also exploring long-term retention and learner engagement to better understand the sustained impact of AI-driven gamified learning.

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